

APPLICATION OF THE TECHNOLOGY OF GAME METHODS IN THE LESSONS AS A WAY TO ACTIVATE STUDENTS

Anarkulova Gulnaz Mirzaxmatovna

Doctor of philosophy (PhD), Associate Professor of the Department of Teaching Methods of Professional Education, Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizami

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7824320>

Abstract. *The content of the article reveals the essence of gaming technology, methods of using gaming methods as factors affecting the effectiveness of training.*

Keywords: *technology, teaching methods, quality of education, role-playing games, the effectiveness of education.*

Reforms in the social sector of Uzbekistan have gained particular momentum. Due to the adoption of a number of important legal documents in the field, it was possible to form a solid foundation for further improvement of the national education system. Taking into account world standards, the material and technical base of schools is being strengthened, curricula and programs are being filled with new content.

At the beginning of 2022, the President of the Republic Sh.M. Mirziyoyev signed the Decree “On Approval of the National Program for the Development of Public Education in 2022-2026” and the Decree “On Additional Measures for the Development of Public Education”.

These documents are aimed at building the knowledge and skills of school students, educating them in the spirit of devotion to national and universal values, increasing the authority of the teaching profession and the quality of teachers, improving textbooks and educational and methodological complexes based on modern requirements, building modern models of public education institutions that meet international standards.

Education is a powerful factor in the development of the spiritual culture of the Uzbek people, the reproduction of the productive forces of society. This humanitarian sphere is aimed at providing fundamental scientific, general cultural, professional and practical training of the individual, the formation of the intellectual potential of the nation and the comprehensive development of the individual as the highest value of society.

The reform in the system of continuous education of the Republic of Uzbekistan sets a task for the teaching staff, both qualified and competitive specialists. The reform strategy is built on the basis of a systematic approach, which we see the transformation of nine-year general education schools into 11-year education.

The basis of such transformations is always the development of new technologies as a combination of traditional and innovative methods and techniques. I would like to emphasize: it is not calls for the modernization of the educational process, not the development of regular improvement and development programs that renews the school. It is updated by a teacher who has mastered modern educational technologies of training and education.

The modern organization of the educational process should guarantee the possibility of mastering the educational material at a high level by each student, ensure his readiness to carry out effective activities in complex, variable, constantly changing conditions.

The work of many foreign and domestic scientists is devoted to the problem of ensuring the quality of education, the work of many scientists is devoted to the problem of ensuring the

quality of education, such as Bepalko V.P., Babansky, Yu.K., Batyshev, S. Ya. , Ilyin, T.A., Selevko, S., Makhmutov, as well as domestic scientists, U.K. Tolipov, N.N. Azizkhodzhaeva, Zh.G.Yulldashev and others.

The conducted studies show that the main way to achieve the quality of training of specialists at the level of modern requirements is the organization of the educational process based on student-centered learning technologies. One of the types of student-centered learning technologies is gaming technology.

Game technologies. The game, along with work and learning, is one of the main types of human activity. A game is a type of activity in situations aimed at recreating and assimilating social experience, in which self-management of behavior is formed and improved.

The structure of the game as an activity organically includes goal setting, planning, goal realization, as well as analysis of the results in which the person fully realizes himself as a subject. Motivation of gaming activity is provided by its voluntariness, opportunities for choice and elements of competition, satisfaction of the need for self-affirmation, self-realization.

The value of the pedagogical game cannot be exhausted and assessed by entertaining and recreational opportunities. Its phenomenon lies in the fact that, being entertainment, recreation, it is able to grow into education, creativity, therapy, a model of the type of human relations and manifestations in work.

The implementation of game techniques and situations in the lesson form of classes takes place in the following main areas: the didactic goal is set for students in the form of a game task; educational activity is subject to the rules of the game; educational material is used as its means, an element of competition is introduced into educational activity, which translates the didactic task into a game one; successful completion of the didactic task is associated with the game result.

The place and role of game technology in the educational process, the combination of game and learning elements largely depends on the teacher's understanding of the functions and classifications of pedagogical games.

In the pedagogical process, the game acts as a method of training and education, the transfer of accumulated experience, starting from the first steps of "human society along the path of its development. Selevko G.K. notes: "In a modern school, which relies on the activation and intensification of the educational process, game activity is used in the following cases:

- *as independent technologies for mastering a concept, topic, and even a section of a subject;*
- *as elements (sometimes quite essential) of a larger technology;*
- *as a lesson (class) or part of it (introduction, explanation, consolidation, exercise, control);*
- *as a technology of extracurricular activities.*

Application in the lessons Technology of game methods:

Role-playing games are characterized by the presence of a task or problem and the distribution of roles between the participants in its solution.

Role-playing creates interdependence of students in the lesson and thereby activates their cognitive and creative activity.

"Exhibition of National Embroidery Products".

Grade 5 Topic: Using national types of patterns when embroidering. The teacher distributes several types of national types of patterns, reports the topic and purpose of the lesson. The teacher

invites the children to imagine that they are preparing products for an international exhibition of national crafts. When organizing an exhibition, someone takes part as a jury, someone as an exhibitor. Each participant performs his task according to the assigned role. After 20 minutes, change roles. At the end of the lesson, each participant not only in embroidery, but also in the evaluation of the product has an idea.

In modeling games, it is desirable to include certain conflicts of interests of group members. This allows you to bring the game model closer to real processes. During the game, the participants do not have all the data for making the optimal decision, interference is introduced into their actions that make it difficult to complete the task. For a business game that simulates a real situation, it is important to encourage each participant to act as in a real situation. It is important to coordinate the actions of the participants in the game. In individual episodes, a situation may arise when some participants must subordinate their interests to others for the successful operation of the group as a whole. It is necessary to emphasize the contribution of each participant to the current and final results of the game; for this, intermediate and boundary control is required for all members of the game group.

REFERENCES

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, dated May 11, 2022, No. UP-134, approving the national program for the development of public education in 2022-2026.
2. Azizkhodzhaeva N.N. Pedagogical technologies and pedagogical skills. Chulpan Publishing and Printing Creative House, Tashkent – 2005
3. Anarkulova G.M. Pedagogical management and pedagogical skills. Scientific journal “Young scientist” No. 9 (89), May., 2015. 1021-1023.
4. Anarkulova G.M. Parpiev O.T. The use of pedagogical games in the SSVE system. Toolkit. T.2007